

TECHNOLOGIES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIALLY ACTIVE CIVIC COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS BY WRITING A DISCUSSION TEXT USING PORTABLE MEANING WORDS

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Annotation: the pedagogical skills of the teacher of the native language and the presence of sufficient theoretical knowledge in science “do you know your deputy?” in its detailed coverage, it helps in the development of socially active civic competence in students, but only by telling or lecturing theoretical information does not guarantee quality education to the student. Today's readers are curious in every way, they like exhibitionism. This article will mention the methods that can be applied to the teacher in explaining the topic on the basis of innovation and integration in this regard, their advantages.

Keywords: pedagogical skill, exhibitionism, Freethought, reading comprehension, listening comprehension, colloquial competence, linguistic competence, election, MP, lexicographical meaning, ambiguous word, own meaning, portable meaning.

In our country, special attention has been paid to the field of education since the first years of independence. Today it can also be seen that the focus on education is improving in secondary schools. The foundation for knowledge is laid by a teacher at school, who is supposedly an architect, an decorator, a specialist who starts the child on the right path. The quality of Education also grows if the teacher is a master of his profession, and loves children. The teacher of the native language will learn the difference of state educational standards and curricula from the previous program and DTS, the methodology of teaching innovations in educational regulatory documents based on the content of topics, the implementation of methods of delivering science-related topics to students based on a competency approach, the application of advanced work experiences in the field of science, independently must have competencies in the application of guidance and methods of improving their skills. In addition, it is always recommended that the latest achievements of Science and technology be taken into account when covering topics.

At the request of the DTS, the main goal of teaching the subject of the Uzbek language was embodied in two competencies.

1. Speech competence is the ability to listen and understand, read, speak and write, that is, to master the skills of communication.

2. Linguistic competence refers to the acquisition of language material (phonetics, lexicon, grammar) and tools in order to acquire sufficient knowledge to be able to apply it in speech, and the types of knowledge and speech activity (listening, understanding, reading, speaking, writing).¹

The standard defines language material, language tools and grammatical knowledge, the necessary skills to be generated from each type of speech activity. This requires the correct

¹ Umumiy o‘rta ta’limning milliy o‘quv dasturi. Ona tili (1-11-sinf) 8-b

pronunciation of the studied word and word forms and the appropriate use of literary language capabilities in writing, grammatically correct word formation, appropriate choice of words, syntactically-methodically correct assessment, sentence construction and speech tone setting. In order to implement these set goals and objectives, Uzbek textbooks provide information on grammar, as well as literary and artistic texts for the development of speech competence, information on the life and work of Uzbek poet-u writers. A reader familiar with this information will develop speech skills from the Uzbek language, seeing the rich samples of the Uzbek literary language and literature. That is, along with linguistic competence, speech, base competencies are also formed, forming the necessary knowledge, skills, qualifications.

Based on the above goals and objectives, we are now talking about the topic "Do you know your deputy?" in the current 6th grade native language textbook in schools where education is carried out in Uzbek?"we want to Share our recommendations about some of the techniques and techniques that will be used in the development of educational and educational competencies of students by teaching them.

It is known that the election is a free choice of citizens, to participate in the administration of power or in the passage of laws through the representative of their choice. Elections are based on general, equal, direct and secret ballot principles. The fact that students have knowledge about elections helps in an increase in their legal, political consciousness and worldview, that is, their socially active civil competence — to feel the immunity to what is happening in society, phenomena and processes, to actively participate in them, to know their civil duty and rights, to comply with it, to work, to be treated in civil relations,²

In the process of teaching subjects, various classes, extracurricular activities, excursions and extracurricular activities play an important role in the content of socially active civic competence in students.

The pedagogical skills of the native language teacher and the availability of sufficient theoretical knowledge in science will help in the detailed coverage of this topic, the development of socially active civil competence in students, but knowledge only by telling or lecturing theoretical information does not guarantee quality education. Today's readers are curious in every way, they like exhibitionism. Therefore, the methods used by the teacher in explaining the topic occupy an important place in this regard.

DO YOU KNOW YOUR MP?

Lesson objectives:

a) educational purpose:

- formation of the ability to react to text in readers;
- absorption of vocabulary and grammatical meanings of words.

b) educational purpose:

- educating students in a national and patriotic spirit;
- instilling the Democratic electoral system in the minds of the younger generation;
- to achieve the formation of political and legal consciousness.

² Umumiy o'rta ta'limning milliy o'quv dasturi. Ona tili (1-11-sinf) 10-b

d) developing goal: the formation of speech competencies in students, such as listening and understanding, reading, speaking and writing.

I. Students learn on this topic:

- obligations of the deputies elected by the people, their position in the development of the country;
- the importance of the election;
- writing a discussion text;
- critical thinking;
- consistent expression of thought;
- distinguish word categories;
- distinguish between portable meanings of words.

That is, educational and educational competencies develop-they feel that they are involved in the processes taking place in society, they know that participation in them is the civil duty of each, they acquire treatment and legal culture in civil relations.

II. Before entering a new topic, students will answer the following questions:

1. Who do you think is a deputy?
2. What can the election of Deputies change?
3. Which MP did you meet? What topics did you talk about?

Through this question-and-answer, readers exchange opinions about all their knowledge of the election. The answers are summarized by the teacher.

III. Audiomatn is listened to. "Who is the MP?". Answer questions. Once an Audiomatn is heard, students answer the following questions based on what they listen to and understand. And through this, their oral speech, legal, political knowledge develop, their worldview expands.

1. What types of power are there?
2. What types of deputy are there?
3. How does lawmakers work out monthly?
4. How do you imagine working on a public basis?
5. What is the main requirement of the deputy?
6. Whose representatives are the deputies?
7. Who do you think MPs should work for?

Through this exercise, students develop a listening comprehension skill, that is, they perceive the speech of others, comprehend the content. Students' answers are listened to and summarized, summarized, evaluated on the basis of criteria

IV. Familiarize yourself with the comments to the word "deputy" in the Explanatory Dictionary of the Uzbek language.

MP - [lot. deputetus-represented, sent]

1. The person elected to the competent state body, the representative. For example: deputy of the Supreme Assembly. People's deputy. Elect a deputy.

2. A team (Group), a person represented by an organization to complete a task. For example: Congress deputy.³

³ ЎЗБЕК ТИЛИНИНГ ИЗОҲЛИ ЛУҒАТИ.1-жилд. "Ўзбекистон миллий энциклопедияси" Давлат илмий нашриёти. 559-б.

- Harmonize with the information you receive from the audiomatn and ask "Who Is the Deputy?", write the answer. Through this exercise, the vocabulary wealth of students increases, the ability to perceive, comprehend develops - the skill of listening and understanding develops.
- V. A written exercise is performed.
- MP
- 1. The person elected to the competent state body, the representative.
- 2. Team (group), the person whom the organization represents to complete a task...
- Through this type of exercise, the student's writing skills develop, that is, his written thoughts are described, observing the rules of grammar and spelling. The mother tongue teacher evaluates students according to the writing skills of a 6th grader given in the following national curriculum:
 - - To be able to write 3-4 interconnected sentences by heart, more broadly;
 - - being able to write short dictations;
 - - being able to transcribe sentences correctly;
 - - being able to write simple sentences based on the grammatical phenomenon or samples studied;
 - - being able to write letters, simple messages to a friend to carry out communication;
 - - being able to translate simple words and learned grammatical phenomena;
 - - to be able to express wishes using the formulas of colloquial etiquette adopted in the country where the language is being studied;
 - - being able to modify and write words and phrases in a sample text, replacing them with other words and combinations of words;
 - - to be able to perform a certain task in writing based on the texts read or listened to;
 - - being able to compose dialogues based on samples;
 - - be able to draw up simple tables, fill them out and describe them in writing;
 - - be able to check if the word is written correctly, use a bilingual dictionary to find forgotten or unfamiliar words.⁴

In place of the conclusion, we must say that the ways of migration of meaning were scientifically studied by world and Uzbek linguists. Based on this studied theoretical data, it is necessary to use innovative and interactive methods related to this topic, develop them and apply them to the educational process in order to explain the migration of meaning to students using texts, activate the application, based on the main goal of teaching the Uzbek language. The implementation of such tasks in the course processes develops socially active civil competencies not only of students, but also of their family members. His indifference to political events in society disappears.

⁴ Umumiy o'rtta ta'limning milliy o'quv dasturi. Ona tili (1-11-sinf) 7-b

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